

*Eight Seminar of Differential Equations
Dynamical Systems & Their Applications
Isfahan University of Technology, Isfahan, Iran
July 19-21, 2008*

Time variant linear systems with time varying delays

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Abstract

Robust stability for uncertain time variant linear systems with time varying delays is studied. Here, we consider the case when the time-delay is continuously differentiable and bounded time-varying function. A new sufficient condition for delay dependent is given in matrix inequality form which is depend on the range of delay function and its derivative. Some numerical examples are given to illustrate and compare our results with others in the literature.

MSC 2000: 35B35;34D20.

keywords: Robust stability, Time delay, Lyapunov-Krasovskii functional, Uncertainty.

1 Introduction and Preliminaries

Dynamical systems with time delays have been of considerable interest for decades. Delay systems represent a class of infinite-dimensional systems largely used to describe economical systems, biology, Neural network. In this paper, we investigate the stability of time variant linear systems with time-varying delay where the delay is time differentiable and bounded with bounded derivative. Since the parameter uncertainties are time varying and unknown, the stability of system is depend on the size of time-delay and its time derivative. In order to establish a new delay-dependent sufficient conditions for robust stability of such a system, using the Lyapunov-Krasovskii functional method with linear matrix inequality (LMI) approach by tuning of some scalars together with the parameterized first-order model transformation.

2 Notations

The following standard notation will be used throughout the paper. Let $\mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ denotes the set of all $n \times m$ real matrices, A^T be the transpose of matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $A < B$ (resp., $A \leq B$) means that the matrix $B - A$ is positive definite for any two symmetric matrices $A, B \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$.

3 Main results

Let us consider the time-varying delay linear system with uncertainty

$$\dot{x}(t) = [A_0 + \Delta A_0(t)] x(t) + [A_1 + \Delta A_1(t)] x(t - \tau(t)), \quad (1)$$

where $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is state vector, $A_0, A_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ are constant matrices and the uncertainties are of the form

$$\Delta A_0(t) = D_0 F_0(t) E_0, \quad \Delta A_1(t) = D_1 F_1(t) E_1, \quad (2)$$

where D_0, E_0, D_1 , and E_1 are appropriate dimensional constant matrices, and $\|F_0(t)\| \leq 1, \|F_1(t)\| \leq 1$ for all t . In addition, the time-delay $\tau(t)$ is time-varying, positive, bounded and continuously differentiable satisfying

$$0 \leq \tau(t) \leq h, \quad \dot{\tau}(t) \leq d < 1. \quad (3)$$

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The goal of this paper is to find criteria for robust stability of the system (1) by using the Lyapunov method in conjunction with LMI techniques. For simplicity, we will write

$$A_0(t) = A_0 + \Delta A_0(t), \quad A_1(t) = A_1 + \Delta A_1(t).$$

Since $x(t)$ is continuously differentiable for $t \geq 0$. By adopting the Leibnitz-Newton formula, we have

$$x(t - \tau(t)) = x(t) - \int_{-\tau(t)}^0 \dot{x}(t + \theta) d\theta = x(t) - \int_{-\tau(t)}^0 [A_0(\theta)x(t + \theta) + A_1(\theta)x(t + \theta - \tau(\theta))] d\theta. \quad (4)$$

Therefore, the system

$$\dot{x}(t) = A_0(t)x(t) + A_1(t)x(t - \tau(t)), \quad (5)$$

can be transferred into a distributed delay system

$$\dot{x}(t) = (A_0(t) + C)x(t) + (A_1(t) - C)x(t - \tau(t)) - C \int_{-\tau(t)}^0 [A_0(\theta)x(t + \theta) + A_1(\theta)x(t + \theta - \tau(\theta))] d\theta, \quad (6)$$

where C is a parametric matrix which derives the stability result less restrictive to some degree. Since in this process only one integration over one delay interval is used, the process is called parameterized first-order model transformation, [2]. The stability of (6) implies the stability of the system (5), see [3] and references therein. We can rewrite the system (6) as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}(t) = & (A_0 + D_0 F_0(t) E_0 + C)x(t) + (A_1 + D_1 F_1(t) E_1 - C)x(t - \tau(t)) - \\ & C \int_{t-\tau(t)}^t [A_0(\theta)x(\theta) + A_1(\theta)x(\theta - \tau(\theta))] d\theta. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where D_0, E_0, D_1, E_1 and F_0, F_1 are as 2.

Since the stability of (7) implies the stability of (6) and consequently the stability of the system (5). We mainly focus on the stability of (7) in main theorem.

The following lemmas will be essential for the proof of the main theorem.

Lemma 1. [4] Let $w(t) = \int_{a(t)}^{b(t)} \int_{t-\theta}^t f(s) ds d\theta$. Then the following is satisfied,

$$\frac{d}{dt} w(t) = (b - a)f(t) - (1 - b) \int_{t-b}^{t-a} f(s) ds + (b - a) \int_{t-a}^t f(s) ds. \quad (8)$$

Lemma 2. [4] Let $a(t) \leq b(t)$. Then, the following inequality holds,

$$\left\| \int_a^b f(s) ds \right\|^2 \leq (b - a) \int_a^b \|f(s)\|^2 ds. \quad (9)$$

Now we present a sufficient condition that guarantees the stability of the system (1) satisfying the uncertainty in (2) and the time -delay in (3).

Theorem 1. Consider the time-delay uncertain system (1) with the uncertainty in(2) and the time delay in (3). The system is robust asymptotically stable, if there exist four positive -definite matrices $P, Q_{10}, Q_{11}, R > 0$, positive constants λ, η_0, η_1 and constant matrix $W \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_1 = & PA_0 + A_0^T P + W + W^T + \frac{1}{\lambda} PD_0 D_0^T P + \lambda E_0^T E_0 + \frac{1}{1-d} (PA_1 - W) R^{-1} (PA_1 - W)^T \\ & + \frac{1}{1-d} PD_1 D_1^T P + W Q_{10}^{-1} W^T + W Q_{11}^{-1} W^T + S_1 + h^2 S_{10}(Q_{10}, \eta_0) + \frac{h^2}{(1-d)^2} S_{11}(Q_{11}, \eta_1) < 0 \end{aligned}$$

Where

$$S_{10}(Q_{10}, \eta_0) := A_0^T Q_{10} A_0 + A_0^T Q_{10} D_0 (\eta_0 I - D_0^T Q_{10} D_0)^{-1} D_0^T Q_{10} A_0 + \eta_0 E_0^T E_0, \quad (10)$$

$$S_{11}(Q_{11}, \eta_1) := A_1^T Q_{11} A_1 + A_1^T Q_{11} D_1 (\eta_1 I - D_1^T Q_{11} D_1)^{-1} D_1^T Q_{11} A_1 + \eta_1 E_1^T E_1, \quad (11)$$

Satisfying

$$(\eta_0 I - D_0^T Q_{10} D_0) > 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (\eta_1 I - D_1^T Q_{11} D_1) > 0 \quad (12)$$

$$S_1 := R + E_1^T E_1. \quad (13)$$

Also, the corresponding model transformation matrix in (7) is given by $C = P^{-1}W$.

Proof. We consider the following Lyapunov-Karasovskii functional

$$V(x(t)) = V_1(x(t)) + hV_2(x(t)) + \frac{h}{(1-d)^2} V_3(x(t)), \quad (14)$$

where

$$V_2(x(t)) := \int_0^h \int_{t-\theta}^t x^T(s) S_{10}(Q_{10}, \eta_0) x(s) ds d\theta, \quad (15)$$

$$V_3(x(t)) := \int_{\tau(t)}^{h+\tau(t)} \int_{t-\theta}^t x^T(s) S_{11}(Q_{11}, \eta_1) x(s) ds d\theta. \quad (16)$$

The system is asymptotically stable if the derivative of the functional is strictly negative. By using lemma 1, we have

$$\frac{d}{dt} V_2(x(t)) = hx^T(t) S_{10}(Q_{10}, \eta_0) x(t) - \int_{t-h}^t x^T(s) S_{10}(Q_{10}, \eta_0) x(s) ds, \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} V_3(x(t)) &= hx^T(t) S_{11}(Q_{11}, \eta_1) x(t) - (1 - \dot{\tau}(t)) \int_{t-h-\tau(t)}^{t-\tau(t)} x^T(s) S_{11}(Q_{11}, \eta_1) x(s) ds \\ &\leq hx^T(t) S_{11}(Q_{11}, \eta_1) x(t) - (1-d) \int_{t-h-\tau(t)}^{t-\tau(t)} x^T(s) S_{11}(Q_{11}, \eta_1) x(s) ds. \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Also, let: $V_1(x(t)) = x^T(t) P x(t) + \int_{t-\tau(t)}^t x^T(\lambda) S_1(\lambda) x(\lambda) d\lambda$, with $P > 0$, then its time derivative along the trajectories of (7) gives

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} V_1(x(t)) &= x^T(t) (PA_0 + A_0^T P + W + W^T) x(t) + \\ &2x^T(t) PD_0 F_0(t) E_0 x(t) + 2x^T(t) (PA_1 - W) x(t - \tau(t)) + \\ &2x^T(t) PD_1 F_1(t) E_1 x(t - \tau(t)) - 2x^T(t) PC \int_{t-\tau(t)}^t A_0(\theta) x(\theta) d\theta - \\ &2x^T(t) W \int_{t-\tau(t)}^t A_1(\theta) x(\theta - \tau(\theta)) d\theta + x^T(t) S_1 x(t) - (1 - \dot{\tau}(t)) x^T(t - \tau(t)) S_1 x(t - \tau(t)). \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Using the following inequalities for any positive real number $\beta > 0$ and any positive definite matrix D ,

$$-2u^T v \leq 2u^T v \leq \beta u^T D^{-1} u + \beta^{-1} v^T D v,$$

where $u, v \in \mathbb{R}^n$, We have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} V_1(x(t)) &\leq x^T(t) (PA_0 + A_0^T P + W + W^T) x(t) + \lambda x^T(t) E_0^T E_0 x(t) + \frac{1}{\lambda} x^T(t) PD_0 D_0^T P x(t) + \\ &\frac{1}{1-d} x^T(t) (PA_1 - W) R^{-1} (PA_1 - W)^T x(t) + (1-d) x^T(t - \tau(t)) R x(t - \tau) + \\ &\frac{1}{1-d} x^T(t) PD_1 D_1^T P x(t) + (1-d) x^T(t - \tau(t)) E_1^T E_1 x(t - \tau(t)) + \\ &2 \| x^T(t) W Q_{10}^{-1/2} \| \cdot \left\| \int_{t-\tau(t)}^t Q_{10}^{1/2} A_0(\theta) x(\theta) d\theta \right\| + \\ &2 \| x^T(t) W Q_{11}^{-1/2} \| \cdot \left\| \int_{t-\tau(t)}^t Q_{11}^{1/2} A_1(\theta) x(\theta - \tau(\theta)) d\theta \right\| + \\ &x^T(t) S_1 x(t) - (1-d) x^T(t - \tau(t)) S_1 x(t - \tau(t)). \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

From [4] we have

$$\begin{aligned} A_0^T(t)Q_{10}A_0(t) &= [A_0 + D_0F_0(t)E_0]^T Q_{10} [A_0 + D_0F_0(t)E_0] \\ &\leq A_0^T Q_{10} A_0 + A_0^T Q_{10} D_0(\eta_0 I - D_0^T Q_{10} D_0)^{-1} D_0^T Q_{10} A_0 + \eta_0 E_0^T E_0 \\ &:= S_{10}(Q_{10}, \eta_0), \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

$$\begin{aligned} A_1^T(t)Q_{11}A_1(t) &= [A_1 + D_1F_1(t)E_1]^T Q_{11} [A_1 + D_1F_1(t)E_1] \\ &\leq A_1^T Q_{11} A_1 + A_1^T Q_{11} D_1(\eta_1 I - \\ &\quad D_1^T Q_{11} D_1)^{-1} D_1^T Q_{11} A_1 + \eta_1 E_1^T E_1 \\ &:= S_{11}(Q_{11}, \eta_1). \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Recall the following relations from [4]

$$\int_{t-\tau(t)}^t \|Q_{10}^{1/2} A_0(\theta)x(\theta)\|^2 d\theta \leq \int_{t-\tau(t)}^t x^T(\theta) S_{10}(Q_{10}, \eta_0) x(\theta) d\theta, \quad (23)$$

$$\int_{t-\tau(t)}^t \|x^T(\theta - \tau(\theta)) A_1^T(\theta) Q_{11}^{1/2}\|^2 d\theta \leq \frac{1}{1-d} \int_{t-\tau(t)-h}^{t-\tau(t)} x^T(\theta) S_{11}(Q_{11}, \eta_1) x(\theta) d\theta, \quad (24)$$

and apply this to (20) to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} V_1(x(t)) &\leq x^T(t)(PA_0 + A_0^T P + W + W^T + \frac{1}{\lambda} P D_0 D_0^T P \\ &\quad + \lambda E_0^T E_0 + \frac{1}{1-d} P D_1 D_1^T P + \frac{1}{1-d} (PA_1 - W) R^{-1} (PA_1 - W)^T) x(t) \\ &\quad + (1-d)x^T(t-\tau(t)) R x(t-\tau(t)) + (1-d)x^T(t-\tau(t)) (R + E_1^T E_1) x(t-\tau(t)) \\ &\quad + x^T(t) W Q_{10}^{-1} W^T x(t) + \tau(t) \int_{t-\tau(t)}^t x^T(\theta) S_{10}(Q_{10}, \eta_0) x(\theta) d\theta \\ &\quad + x^T(t) W Q_{11}^{-1} W^T x(t) + \frac{h}{1-d} \int_{t-\tau(t)-h}^{t-\tau(t)} x^T(\theta) S_{11}(Q_{11}, \eta_1) x(\theta) d\theta \\ &\quad + x^T(t) S_1 x(t) - (1-d)x^T(t-\tau(t)) S_1 x(t-\tau(t)). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}(x(t)) &\leq x^T(t)(PA_0 + A_0^T P + W + W^T + \frac{1}{\lambda} P D_0 D_0^T P \\ &\quad + \lambda E_0^T E_0 + \frac{1}{1-d} P D_1 D_1^T P + \frac{1}{1-d} (PA_1 - W) R^{-1} (PA_1 - W)^T \\ &\quad + W Q_{10}^{-1} W^T + W Q_{11}^{-1} W^T + S_1 + h^2 S_{10}(Q_{10}, \eta_0) + \frac{h^2}{(1-d)^2} S_{11}(Q_{11}, \eta_1)) x(t) < 0. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, if the conditions of theorem hold then, the derivative of the functional is strictly negative which implies asymptotic stability. $\square$

4 Examples

In this section, some numerical examples will be demonstrated, to compare with the previous results.

Example 1. Let us consider the following easy case of the time delay uncertain system:

$$\dot{x}(t) = A_0 x(t) + A_1 x(t - \tau(t)),$$

where $A_0 = \begin{bmatrix} -3 & -2 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$, $A_1 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.5 & 0.1 \\ 0.3 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$, the same as A given in example 2 of [5].

Obviously, In this case we have $\dot{\tau}(t) = 0$ and $d = 0$ in (3). Consequently the maximum delay associated with

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1.923076923 \\ 1.923076923 & 6.130177515 \end{bmatrix}, \quad W = \begin{bmatrix} 0.006 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.03 \end{bmatrix}, \quad Q_{10} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{6} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{6} \end{bmatrix}, \quad Q_{11} = I_{2 \times 2},$$

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} 0.3 & 0 \\ 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \Delta A_0(t) = \Delta A_1(t) = 0, \text{ is obtained as } \tau < 0.9523.$$

whereas, applying the conditions given in [5], the system is stable as $\tau < 0.7062$

Example 2. Let us consider the uncertain time-delay systems with time varying delay describe by the following state equation:

$$\dot{x}(t) = A_0 x(t) + A_1 x(t - \tau(t)) + \Delta A_0 x(t) + \Delta A_1 x(t - \tau(t)),$$

where $A_0 = \begin{bmatrix} -2 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$, $A_1 = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ -1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$, and $\|\Delta A_0(t)\| \leq 0.05$, $\|\Delta A_1(t)\| \leq 0.1$, with

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -0.9 \\ -0.9 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \lambda = 1, \quad R = \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad W = \begin{bmatrix} -0.1 & 0 \\ 0 & -0.5 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$Q_{10} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad Q_{11} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.9 \end{bmatrix},$$

$\eta_1 = 0.2$, $\eta_0 = 0.1$, and $d = 0$. We conclude that the system is stable if $\tau < 0.4661$. This value is larger than $\tau < 0.43$ in [5].

Example 3: consider the same interval system as given in [1]:

$$\dot{x}(t) = A_0(t)x(t) + A_1(t)x(t - \tau),$$

where $A_0(t) = A_0 + \varepsilon_0 \sin^2 t \cdot I_2$, $A_1(t) = A_1 + \varepsilon_1 \cos^2 t \cdot I_2$, such that A_0, A_1 are known 2×2 matrices, ε_0 and ε_1 are uncertain but bounded as $|\varepsilon_0| \leq 1$, $|\varepsilon_1| \leq 1$. Here we assume that

$$A_0 = \begin{bmatrix} -2 & 0 \\ 0 & -1.9 \end{bmatrix}, \quad A_1 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.5 & 0 \\ -0.1 & -0.5 \end{bmatrix},$$

with $P = \begin{bmatrix} 172.2344 & 0 \\ 0 & 140 \end{bmatrix}$, $R = \begin{bmatrix} 86 & 0 \\ 0 & 70 \end{bmatrix}$, $W = \begin{bmatrix} -0.1172 & 0 \\ 0 & -0.1 \end{bmatrix}$, $Q_{10} = Q_{11} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} =$

$D_0 = D_1$, $E_0 = E_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 5 & 0 \\ 0 & 5 \end{bmatrix}$, $\lambda = 3$, $d = 0$, $\eta_0 = \eta_1 = 0.5$. By considering the condition $|\varepsilon_0| \leq 0.35$ and $|\varepsilon_1| \leq 0.35$. we get $h < 0.961671992$ which is greater than $h < 0.73$ of the example in [1] with the same condition.

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